

Implementation of Serving Leadership Style in Dulupi District Office, Boalemo Regency

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the style of serving leadership in the Dulupi District Office, Boalemo Regency. The method in this study uses descriptive qualitative methods with data collection techniques by observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of the study show that the leadership style in the Dulupi sub-district office has not been implemented properly, so there are still things that are lacking and need to be improved and developed again. This can be seen from the various characteristics of servant leadership that need to be improved and further developed, namely listening, empathy, predictability, healing ability, and serving ability.

Therefore, the characteristics of leadership need to be improved and developed again. Good characteristics in government, because the presence of leader characteristics can make employees grow in working well in the work environment and government. The leader is an exemplary example and can provide direction and therefore can create a sense of enthusiasm and openness so that teamwork can work well and correctly to achieve common goals

Keywords: Serving Leadership Style

1. Introduction

The human component in the organization is a determining element in the organization because the organization will experience major problems in achieving its goals if it rejects or ignores the human element. One of the human components in an organization is a leader. Leaders must scan the internal and external environment, chart strategic and task objectives, and provide performance feedback. Leadership is important for motivating followers and mobilizing resources towards the fulfillment of the organization's mission, it is also essential for organizational innovation, adaptation, and performance. Effective organizational leadership is not just about exercising influence on an interpersonal level, effective leadership also depends on leader expertise and on the formulation and implementation of solutions to complex social (and task-oriented). Organizational leaders place organizational members in achieving organizational forms. In carrying out activities

influencing others in achieving organizational goals, leaders have different ways or behaviors from one another and this method is better known as a leadership style. With the magnitude of the responsibility of a leader, the mastery of the leader in influencing subordinates, displays a certain leadership style towards achieving predetermined developments. Where is the behavior of the leader This is known as a leadership style, and the achievement of results is called performance. Research on leadership provides an interesting memory research because it always explains how to be a good leader, attitudes, styles, and serving that are by the leadership situation, and the requirements of a good leader, to be able to move his subordinates so they can carry out their duties and responsibilities to participate in government activities. Based on initial observations made at the Dulupi Sub-District Office, the Sub-District Head is still far from being consistent or optimal in carrying out his duties as a leader, so there are still employees who arrive late and leave early, sometimes there are even employees who are late at office hours during the morning assembly, not again Employees who sometimes delay in their work. This leads to people sometimes finding it difficult to approach the employees they are going to meet, so they have to come back another day. This requires the attention of a leader to motivate so that employees can work effectively and efficiently so that organizational goals can be carried out properly. It is proven that leaders must always give authority and responsibility to employees to fulfill work and involve employees in making decisions, and leaders always ask for advice, and even respond properly to suggestions and criticism from their subordinates, it's just that employees need concern from leaders when carrying out his job. Management is a process carried out by someone to manage something done individually or in groups. Management is considered very important in achieving a goal that has been planned or determined individually or as a group. Management can be interpreted as the art of organizing and executing. Management is considered very important in human life, especially in managing personal life and when being part of an organization in schools, campuses, offices, and society. In management there are elements (tools of management) that are often referred to as 6M, each element has its explanation

1) Man (Human)

Human resources are the most important and primary element and are considered very strategic. If human resources will not be easy to achieve.

2) Money

Financial management is also considered very important in the process of achieving targets or goals to support the success of the organization/company. Financial management must emphasize and carry out principles.

3) Materials

Materials or often referred to as semi-finished materials (raw materials) and finished materials. In carrying out an effort to achieve targets or goals, the most important or main thing is human resources who have expertise in their fields and use materials or materials. Because these two things cannot be separated.

4) Methods

To achieve the goals or targets that have been planned, a good method is needed to achieve the targets that have been planned. Therefore, humans are the main element in carrying out a method.

5) Machines

In the world of education, organizations/companies need a machine. Because the use of machines makes a business or process easier. Because work efficiency and effectiveness is the main thing.

6) Market (Market)

Marketing a product or goods is something that needs to be done by existing human resources.

Human resource management is a study in the field of management science (read: Definition of Management) that combines psychological, sociological, and other theories. Its real application includes the design and implementation of planning, staffing, career management, employee development, performance evaluation, and employment relations. Human resource management involves policies and decisions that affect the workforce.

Leadership comes from the words lead (lead), leader (leader), and lead (leading). In KBBI each of these words is defined as follows:

<i>Lead</i>	(in a state of) being guided; led
<i>Leader</i>	The one who leads, the guide, the guide
<i>Leading</i>	Knowing or leading, winning the most, holding hands while walking (to lead, show the way, and so on); guide, guide, train so that they can do it themselves
<i>Leadership</i>	About leadership, how to lead

Source: www.kbbi.web.id

From the KBBI definition above, each of these words has its emphasis. Lead shows the situation or circumstances, the leader shows the subject or person, leads shows the process, while leadership emphasizes the ability and way of a person to lead.

In its development, in terms of terminology, the definition of leadership is quite diverse, put forward by experts according to the discipline and field of expertise the experts come from.

As well as developments from the latest findings which have resulted in different perspectives on leadership.

Leadership Theory

1) Excess Theory

This theory assumes that a person will become a leader if he has an advantage over his followers.

2) Nature Theory

This theory states that a person can be a good leader if he has positive traits so that his followers can become good followers, with general leadership traits.

3) Theory of Heredity

According to this theory, a person becomes a leader because of heredity or inheritance, because his parents are leaders, their children will automatically become leaders and will replace their parents.

4) Charismatic Theory

The theory states that a person becomes a leader because that person has charisma (a very big influence).

5) Talent Theory

This theory is also called the ecological theory, which argues that leaders are born because of their talent. He becomes a leader because he does have the talent to be a leader.

Functions and characteristics of leadership

The leadership function relates to social situations in group/organizational life where the leadership function must be manifested in interactions between individuals. Operationally the main functions of leadership can be distinguished as follows:

1) Instructive Function

This function is one-way communication, the leader as the communicator is the party that

2) Consultative Function

This function is a two-way communication. In the first stage to make decisions, leaders often require material considerations which require them to consult with the people they lead, who are considered to have various information materials needed in making decisions. established and is in progress.

3) Participation Function

In carrying out this function the leader tries to activate the people he leads, both in participating in making decisions and in carrying them out.

4) Delegation function

This function is carried out by providing delegation of authority to make or determine decisions, either through approval or without approval from the leadership.

5) Control Function

The Control Function means that successful/effective leadership can manage the activities of its members in a directed and effective coordination, to enable the maximum achievement of common goals.

Leaders are people who lead groups of two or more people, both organizations and families. Leadership is the ability of a leader to control, lead, and influence the thoughts, feelings, or behavior of other people to achieve the goals that have been set predetermined. Leaders consist of formal leaders (formal leaders) and informal leaders (informal leaders). A formal leader is a person (male or female) who is appointed by a certain organization (private or government) (based on appointment letters from the organization concerned) to assume a position in the existing organizational structure with all rights and obligations related to it to achieve the goals of the organization that were set earlier.

Leadership is an ability inherent in a leader who depends on various external factors. Leadership is a person's skill and ability to influence the behavior of others, both those with a higher or lower position than him in thinking and acting so that behavior that may initially be individualistic and egocentric changes into organizational behavior.

Leadership is a person's ability to control or influence other people or different communities towards certain achievements. So, leadership or leadership are characteristics that must be possessed by a leader, which in practice have consequences for the self, which include the following:

1) Must have the courage to make firm and precise decisions (decision making)

- 2) Must have the courage to accept the risk itself
- 3) Must have the courage to accept own responsibility (The Principle of Absoluteness of Responsibility).

The Scope of Leadership in Organizations

Leadership Theory knows about leader behavior, leadership concepts, main duties and functions as well as professional ethics that leaders need to understand. Leadership Techniques examines the technical abilities and skills of leaders. The application of leadership theories includes the concept of the leader's thinking, the leader's behavior, and the ability to use resources. In general, leadership can be interpreted as a process of directing and influencing the task activities of people in groups. Leadership means involving other people, namely the subordinates or employees who will be led. Leadership also involves the sharing of power (Power). Leaders have more power than those who are led. This power comes from several sources, including Reward power, Coercive power, Legitimate power, Referent power, and Expert power.

Leadership History

In the times, leadership was scientifically developed, along with the growth of scientific management in the early 20th century and later developed into a science of leadership. Then it is no longer based on talent and experience alone but prepares in a planned way, and trains new prospective leaders. Everything is done through systematic planning, experimentation, research, analysis, supervision, and mentoring to awaken the qualities of superior leaders so that they are successful in their duties. The value of leadership is no longer determined by natural talent. However, its ability to move many people to do work together, thanks to influence leadership obtained through training and education.

Leaders and Leadership are like a coin that cannot be separated, in the sense that they can be studied separately but must be seen as one unit. A leader must have a leadership spirit, and a leadership spirit possessed by a leader cannot be obtained quickly and immediately, but a process that is formed from time to time until it finally crystallizes into a characteristic.

Leadership style is the way a person takes to practice leadership. Leadership style is not a talent. Therefore, leadership styles can be learned and practiced and their application must be adapted to the situation at hand. Leadership style can also be interpreted as a behavioral norm that is used by someone when that person tries to influence the behavior of others as he sees it.

Leadership style is the overall pattern of a leader's actions, both visible and invisible to his subordinates. Leadership style describes a consistent combination of philosophy, skills, traits, and attitudes that underlie a person's character. The leadership style that shows directly, a leader's belief in the strength of his subordinates. That is, leadership style is behavior and strategy, as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits, and attitudes that are often applied by a leader when he tries to the performance of his subordinates.

In general, every leader is required to carry out several actions related to his leadership. These actions are very influential for the progress of the organization they lead, these actions are: analyzing the organization or group they lead; fostering organizational structures, taking initiatives, achieving organizational goals, providing facilities for communicating; Creating cohesiveness; Developing a sense of happiness for all members of the organization; Sinality (unify/unify); Must work using the philosophy of the organization

he leads. Activities so that the process of serving takes place routinely and continuously covering the entire life of the organization in society. The process in question is carried out in connection with mutual fulfillment of needs between the recipient and the service provider.[6]

Service is a form of service activity carried out by government agencies, both central, regional, BUMN, and BUMD, which are goods and services to meet the needs of the community following applicable laws and regulations.

Service consists of four factors, namely:

- 1) Systems, procedures, and methods
- 2) Personnel, especially emphasized apparatus behavior
- 3) Facilities and infrastructure
- 4) Communities as customers

The main characteristic that distinguishes servant leadership from other leadership models is the desire to lead.

The six most dominant characteristics of servant leadership are:

- 1) Listening

Traditionally, leaders have been valued for their communication skills and ability to communicate decision-making. Servant leaders must reinforce this important skill by demonstrating a deep commitment to listening intensively to the ideas or words of others. Servant leaders seek to identify and understand the will of the group. They try to listen responsively to what is said (and not said). Listen and understand what the body, soul, and mind are communicating.

- 2) Empathy

Servant leaders strive to understand and empathize with others. People need to be accepted and recognized as special and unique individuals. Each individual does not want his presence in an organization/company to be rejected by others around him. The most successful servant leaders are those who can be empathetic listeners.

- 3) Ability to Foresee

The ability to take into account conditions that have already occurred or predict the likely outcome of a situation is difficult to define but easy to identify. People know when they see it. Foresight is a trait that enables servant leaders to understand the lessons of the past, the realities of the present, and the possible consequences of a decision for the future. This sinks the heart of the matter deep into the intuitive mind. So, the ability to foresee was one of the characteristics of a servant leader that he was born with. All other characteristics can be developed consciously. Awareness and perception). Awareness of self and the presence of others can help strengthen servant leaders. Awareness also helps in understanding issues involving ethics and values. This allows people to view most situations from a more integrated position

- 4) Healing Ability

Learning to heal is a powerful force for change and integration. One of the great strengths of servant leadership is the ability to heal oneself and others. Many people are discouraged and suffer from various emotional problems. Even though this is something that is natural in human life, a servant leader must be able and have the opportunity to move the hearts and give enthusiasm to those who relate to them.

- 5) Ability to serve

Peter Block (author of the book *Stewardship and Empowered Manager*) defines the ability to serve (stewardship) in the sense of "holding something with the trust of others". In an organization, every level of management, from top management to the shop floor all has an important role to play in holding the organization in faith in the greater good of society. Servant leadership, like the ability to serve, is first and foremost a commitment to serve the needs of others. This of course emphasizes openness and honesty, not control or supervision.

a. Forms of Service

General forms of service are divided into three types as follows:

1) Oral service

Oral services are carried out by employees in public relations, information, and other fields who must provide explanations or information to anyone who needs service. For oral services to be successful by expectations, some conditions must be met by service providers, including:

- a.) Understand the problems that exist in their field
- b.) Provide the necessary explanations smoothly, correctly, briefly, and clearly
- c) Be polite and friendly
- d.) Discipline

2) Service with writing

Service with writing is the most prominent form of service in carrying out tasks. Not only in terms of quantity but also in terms of service. Writing services are quite efficient, especially for services that are provided remotely due to the cost factor. Services with writing are divided into two parts, namely:

- a.) Services in the form of information guides and the like aimed at people who have an interest in making it easier to deal with agencies.
- b.) Services in the form of written documents on requests, complaints, grants, reports, and notifications.

3) Services in the form of deeds

Services in the form of deeds are usually combined with verbal services. This is due to most oral relationships being carried out in a service relationship and focus more on the actions awaited by the people concerned. The main goal is to get services in the form of actions or results of actions, not just verbal explanations and/or abilities.

2. Methods

This research method uses a qualitative approach, qualitative research is a type of research whose findings are not obtained through statistical processing or other forms of calculation and aims to reveal symptoms in a holistic-contextual manner through collecting data from natural backgrounds by utilizing the researcher himself as a key instrument. Qualitative research is descriptive and tends to use analysis with an inductive approach. Processes and meanings based on the subject's perspective are highlighted in qualitative research.

Initially, qualitative research methods were used more in the field of cultural anthropology, so they were often referred to as ethnographic methods. Qualitative research

methods are also often referred to as naturalistic research methods because the research is carried out in natural conditions or as it is. Thus, the conditions when the researcher entered the field, while in the field, and after leaving the field, the conditions of the object under study remained relatively unchanged.

The instrument in qualitative research is the researcher himself (human instrument). In this case the researcher is the key instrument. It is the researcher who determines the research focus, selects informants as data sources, selects data quality, interprets data, and draws conclusions based on his findings. Data in qualitative research is descriptive data which is generally in the form of words, pictures, or recordings.

Descriptive research is research that seeks to describe an event phenomenon, an event that is happening now. Descriptive research focuses on actual problems as they were at the time the research took place. Through descriptive research, researchers try to describe events and events that are the center of attention without giving special treatment to these events. The variables studied can be single (one variable) or more than one variable.

3. Results

Listening

Leaders are still not good at being active listeners and are still not effective in providing solutions when problems occur, so there are still several complaints from employees or their subordinates. This needs to be developed more maturely.

Empathy

Leaders have an attitude of empathy for employees, but it needs to be developed further because there are still complaints from employees about the empathy that is owned by the leader.

Ability to Foresee

The leader can also help understand issues involving ethics and values, but few leaders have this, so it needs to be further developed.

Healing Ability

Leaders have shown their ability to heal. The thing that the leader does is to continue to provide enthusiasm even though sometimes the leader feels a lack of enthusiasm, but there is still something lacking so it needs to be developed further in healing so that employees and the organization can run well.

Ability to Serve

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that the leadership has shown its ability to serve, he is quite good and tries to serve employees. Regarding serving employees and the organization, the leadership has done well, but only a few are lacking in leadership in serving, this needs to be developed further. so that the company runs well again and progresses in the future.

4. Discussion

Leaders' characteristics play an important role in employee engagement, motivation, acceptance, and participation which in the end leads to enhancing performance and creativity. Many researchers have confirmed the positive and significant relationship between

leadership styles and employee creativity. Some studies also indicated the role of a leader in implementing new strategies and how her/his characteristics/charisma impact the innovation in the organization.

Similar to authentic leadership, servant leadership also acknowledges the importance of being authentic in one's interaction with others. For servant leaders, the propensity to operate with a deep clarity of self-awareness and self-regulation might spring from a spiritual and/or altruistic motive to serve others, both of which are absent in the authentic leadership framework. That is, servant leaders are authentic not for the sake of being authentic, but because they are driven either by a sense of a higher calling or inner conviction to serve and make a positive difference for others.

Relative to ethical leadership, servant leadership more explicitly incorporates stewardship as an essential element of effective leadership, this brings a focus on a long-term perspective that takes into account all stakeholders. Leader behavior in line with ethical leadership theory may have a more prescriptive character and be aligned with rules that one should follow in terms of what is good based on innate ethical rules, but servant leader behavior is more flexible and contingent, taking more explicitly both the follower and the organizational context into account.

Listening

In particular, listening is done patiently for any problems faced by employees as well as providing responses and suggestions encountered. As stated by Veri Widodo, leaders are valued for their communication skills and ability to make decisions. Servant leaders must reinforce this important skill by demonstrating deep commitment, in listening intensively to the ideas or words of others. Servant leaders seek to identify and understand the will of the group. They try to listen responsively to what is said (and not said). Listen and understand what the body, soul, and mind are communicating.

Empathy

Servant leaders strive to understand and empathize with others. As a leader, you must have empathy for your subordinates. A person's ability to understand other people's feelings and problems, to think from other people's points of view, and to respect other people's different views on things.

Ability to Foresee

The ability to predict, namely awareness about the future, not to happen as before or in the past. To solve problems in the future that cannot be ascertained, we must always try to solve them with an approach according to actual behavior, as well as in forecasting. Forecasting is the art and science of predicting future events.

Healing Ability

One of the great strengths of servant leadership is the ability to heal oneself and others. A servant leader tries to help people solve problems and conflicts that occur.

Ability to serve

Servant leadership is leadership developed to overcome a leadership crisis experienced by a society or nation. Servant leaders tend to prioritize the needs, interests, and aspirations of the people they lead above themselves.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The implementation of characteristics implemented in the Dulupi sub-district office have not been carried out properly, so there are still things that are lacking and need to be improved and further developed. This can be seen from the various characteristics of servant leadership that need to be improved and further developed, namely:

- **Listening**, in listening there are interview results based on that the leader is still it is not good to be an active listener and still not optimal in providing solutions when problems occur, so there are still several complaints from employees.
- **Empathy**, in empathy there are interview results that show that leaders have an empathetic attitude towards employees, but it needs to be developed further because there are still complaints from employees about the empathy possessed by leaders.
- **The ability to predict**, the results of interviews with leaders can work well and the awareness of these leaders can also help understand issues involving ethics and values, but leaders lack these skills, so they need to be further developed.
- **Ability to heal**, there are results of interviews with leaders who have shown their ability to heal. The thing that the leadership does is to continue to provide enthusiasm even though sometimes the leadership feels lacking in enthusiasm, but there is still something lacking so it needs to be developed further in healing so that employees and the organization can run well.
- **Ability to serve**, there are results of interviews with leaders who have shown their ability to serve, he is quite good and tries to serve employees. Regarding serving employees and the organization, the leadership has done well, but only a few are lacking in leadership in serving.

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